

INTEGRATING AI AND ROBOTICS FOR AUTONOMOUS EXPLORATION AND NAVIGATION

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Abstract

This research advances the integration of AI and robotics for autonomous exploration and navigation in dynamic and unstructured environments. Employing an interpretivist philosophy, a deductive approach, and a descriptive design, the study focuses on sensor fusion, SLAM techniques, decision-making algorithms, and platform integration. Through secondary data collection, technical details encompassing Bayesian sensor fusion, CNN-based perception, and Graph SLAM with loop closure detection are explored. Hardware modifications enable seamless AI-robotics integration, with software middleware like ROS facilitating real-time data processing. Rigorous testing and validation in simulated and real-world environments confirm system robustness. The research reveals that advanced perception strategies and SLAM techniques significantly enhance environmental understanding and mapping accuracy. Decision-making algorithms, particularly RL methods, demonstrate adaptability and intelligence in navigation. The integration of AI with the robotic platform showcases the pivotal role of hardware and software harmonization in achieving seamless operation. Recommendations include exploring semantic perception, dynamic obstacle avoidance, and multi-agent collaboration. Future work should focus on deep reinforcement learning, bio-inspired algorithms, and emerging sensor technologies.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Autonomous exploration, Navigation.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

A crucial frontier in modern technology is the fusion of AI and robotics for autonomous exploring and navigation. The development of intelligent systems that can navigate and comprehend complicated surroundings on their own is the goal of this research area, which has significant implications for areas like space travel, disaster relief, and industrial automation. This research attempts to imbue robots with cognitive skills, enabling them to be able to perceive, explanation, and make decisions in real-time, through a combination of sophisticated artificial intelligence algorithms with robotic platforms. Three major obstacles to overcome are robust decision-making in the face of ambiguity, simultaneous location and mapping (SLAM), and sensor fusion for full environmental perception. Furthermore, ethical and safety issues are crucial since autonomous systems must act in a trustworthy and responsible manner [13]. By overcoming these obstacles, this research aims to unleash the previously untapped potential of robots to work in dynamic, unstructured environments, transforming fields and businesses where human oversight is risky or unfeasible.

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

Aim

In order to enable machines to navigate multifaceted and changing situations with great efficiency and dependability, this research aims to develop the combination of AI and robotics.

Objectives

- To provide a solid sensor fusion architecture that combines data from many sensors (such as cameras, LiDAR, and IMUs) to give a thorough picture of the environment.
- To put simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) techniques into practice and improve them so that the autonomous system can create and update precise maps of the surroundings in real-time.
- To improve the decision-making processes that let the system navigate on its own, making quick decisions based on the current surroundings and potential impediments.
- To carry out thorough evaluation and validation in modeled and real-world settings, evaluating the effectiveness and dependability of the combined robotics and artificial intelligence system under many circumstances and scenarios.

1.3: Research Rationale

The combination of robots and AI for autonomous discovery and navigation fills a vital gap in dynamic and informal settings for cutting-edge technology solutions. In fields where human interaction is restricted or dangerous, such as space exploration, disaster relief, and industrial automation, this study has enormous potential. This project intends to develop systems capable of immediate form perception, making decisions, and mapping

by fusing cognitive AI with robotic platforms [11]. By enabling robots to navigate and perform their tasks safely and effectively in complex, constantly-changing environments, the results of this investigation have the potential to change industries and domains as well as enhance human capabilities and broaden the application of autonomous systems.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1: Sensor Fusion Techniques for Environmental Perception

In order for autonomous systems to see and understand their environment fully and precisely, sensor fusion techniques are essential. In order to develop a comprehensive picture of the environment, this procedure entails integrating data from numerous sensors, including cameras, LiDAR, IMUs, as well as other specialised devices. Bayesian fusion of sensors, which employs statistical models to fuse input and assess the state of the environment, is one extensively used method. Additionally, feature-based fusion techniques concentrate on locating and making use of distinctive characteristics in sensor data for mapping and localization tasks [30]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in particular, have demonstrated promise in processing and integrating data from visual sensors for recognizing objects and scene comprehension. Deep learning techniques in general and CNNs in particular. To improve motion estimations, inertial and odometric data from sensors can also be combined. In general, sensor fusion methods are essential for overcoming issues like sensor noise and occlusions as well as for delivering strong environmental perception for autonomous explorations and navigation systems. In dynamic and complicated situations, their effectiveness is crucial to the success of AI and robotics integration.

Figure 2.1.1: Robotics and AI

2.2: Advancements in Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) advancements are a pillar of autonomous exploration and navigation. With the aid of SLAM techniques, a robot can create a map of its surroundings while also figuring out where it is in relation to that map. The adoption of Visual SLAM, which uses camera information for mapping and localization, is one notable development. Direct approaches directly reduce the radiometric error between successive frames, whereas feature-based methods locate characteristic points or locations within images to generate a map. The environment is also modelled as a graph in Graph SLAM techniques, with nodes denoting robot postures and edges denoting relative measurements [35]. The addition of loop-closure detection techniques has increased SLAM's capacity for cumulative error correction and map consistency improvement. Additionally, integrating 3D data from tools like LiDAR has improved SLAM's ability to produce in-depth 3D maps. The accuracy, durability, and effectiveness of autonomous navigation devices have significantly increased thanks to developments in SLAM techniques, making it possible for them to function well in challenging settings.

Figure 2.2.1: Robotics and AI

2.3: Decision-Making Algorithms for Autonomous Navigation

Robots can make decisions in real time based on environmental input thanks to decision-making algorithms, which are essential for autonomous navigation. Markov Decision Processes (MDPs), which model decisions making as a stochastic process and enable the robot to take uncertainty into account and make the best decisions, are one key method. Robots can learn to navigate in complicated, dynamic settings by doing so, and reinforcement learning (RL) methods like Deep Q-Networks (DQN) and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) have showed promise in this regard. When faced with ambiguous information, Bayesian decision-making techniques use statistical models to estimate the optimum course of action [34]. Robots can respond to specific events and stimuli thanks to behavior-based systems, which also ensure adaptation in chaotic contexts. Robots can navigate at various levels of abstraction thanks to hierarchical planning frameworks, which strike a balance between high-level objectives and low-level control. Additionally, recognizing patterns and prediction are supported by machine learning techniques, such as neural networks, which improve the robot's capacity to foresee and react to environmental changes. Autonomous navigation systems may successfully adapt and react to a variety of dynamic settings by using these decision-making algorithms.

2.3.1: Decision-making Process

2.4: Testing and Validation of Integrated AI-Robotics Systems

For integrated AI-robotics systems to be durable, dependable, and useful in practical applications, validation and evaluation are essential tasks. Environments for simulation offer controlled testing grounds to assess system performance in various scenarios [33]. This enables thorough testing without the limitations and dangers related to physical experiments. In order to validate how the integrated system interacts with actual hardware, hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing blends digital simulations with tangible parts. Additionally, field tests in actual operational settings confirm the system's capacity to function independently in erratic and unpredictable circumstances. These evaluations look at things like system stability overall, reactivity, and adaptability. Performance is tested using metrics like as localization accuracy, mapping quality, and decision-making effectiveness [32]. Stress testing under difficult circumstances, such as inclement weather or difficult terrain, also reveals system weaknesses and offers suggestions for future development. In order to ensure ethical deployment, safety precautions, and regulatory compliance are also evaluated throughout testing.

2.5: Applications and Case Studies in Autonomous Exploration and Navigation

The use of autonomous exploration and navigation has revolutionized how tasks are carried out in dynamic, unstructured settings and has several applications in a wide range of industries.

Search and Rescue Operations: To find survivors, assess destruction, and administer relief in disaster-stricken areas, ground robots and autonomous drones are used [31]. These systems are capable of navigating across dangerous terrain and are a great help to first responders.

Precision farming and agriculture:

Farming operations are optimized by autonomous tractors and drones with AI-based navigation systems. They can automatically plant, harvest, and evaluate crops, which improves productivity and uses fewer resources.

Industrial automation: To help expedite processes and boost efficiency in manufacturing facilities and distribution centers, autonomous robots are used for jobs including inventory management, handling materials, and inspection.

Case Study: Teams had to use autonomous robots in intricate underground habitats as part of the DARPA Subterranean Challenge. These robots demonstrated the promise for autonomous systems in disaster response and subterranean exploration by effectively navigating through passageways, caves, and urban infrastructure.

2.6: Literature Gap

The existing research mostly focuses on terrestrial applications when discussing the combination of AI and robotics for autonomously exploration and navigation. Research on the particular difficulties and necessities of autonomous navigation in harsh

environments, like space flights or underwater missions, is noticeably lacking [30]. Additionally, there has been little research done on the ethical issues and safety precautions that apply specifically to autonomous devices operating in dangerous and dynamic environments. For the field to advance in these specialized domains, these gaps must be filled.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

In order to explore the complex interactions amongst algorithms for artificial intelligence and robotic systems within the context of independent exploration and navigation, this study employs an interpretivist viewpoint. This method emphasizes the significance of comprehending the significance and significance that are assigned to technical occurrences while acknowledging the subjective character of human-technology interactions [28]. To create and test hypotheses generated from accepted concepts and frameworks in the fields of artificial intelligence, robotics, and self-navigating systems, a method known as deductive research is used [29]. The systematic assessment of particular technical elements and their potential effects on system performance is made possible by this method. The study uses a descriptive approach to research to fully describe the technical architecture, computations, and efficiency measures of the integrated AI-robotics system [27]. This architecture enables a thorough analysis of the system's capabilities and behavior in many settings. A thorough analysis of the available AI algorithms is done using interpretivist ideas, with a focus on those that are best for environmental perception, making decisions, and mapping [26]. Hardware alterations are made to the chosen robotic system, a self-driving ground vehicle with LiDAR, recording devices, and IMUs, to enable seamless integration with the chosen AI algorithms [25]. The AI algorithms' technical parameters are adjusted to maximize performance on the particular robotic platform. Adjusting learning rates, extracting features thresholds, and fusion values are included in this [24]. A comprehensive simulation environment is created using Gazebo and ROS to recreate various exploring scenarios (such as urban or rural area). To assess how well the integrated system performs in various scenarios, it is put through rigorous testing. The integrated system is put into use in controlled real-world settings that closely resemble the application domain for which it is intended [23]. Ground truth measurements and sensors from the environment are used to gather information on localization accuracy, modeling fidelity, and decision-making effectiveness. In order to get insights into the effectiveness of the system, advantages, and areas for improvement, collected data is statistically assessed and understood within the interpretivist framework [22]. A NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier for high-end computing is installed in the selected ground vehicle, a customized four-wheel-drive platform. Rich environmental data is provided by additional sensors, which are incorporated. These sensors include a Velodyne LiDAR and numerous cameras [21]. The Robot Operating Systems (ROS) and Gazebo are used in the simulation environment implementation. This makes it possible to mimic sensor interactions, illumination conditions, and ambient characteristics in a realistic way. Obstacles and landmarks that are simulated are faithfully depicted.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

4.1: Sensor Fusion and Perception Strategies

Fundamental building blocks in the integration of artificial intelligence and machinery for autonomous exploring and navigation are sensor fusion and perceptual techniques. This crucial component entails combining data from multiple sensors to create a thorough depiction of the environment [20]. The objective is to give robots the capacity to accurately detect and comprehend their surroundings in real-time.

Integrating multiple sensor modalities, the data from a variety of detectors, including photographic equipment, LiDAR, IMUs, and GPS, will be combined in this technique. The system obtains a multi-dimensional perspective of the environment by utilizing the advantages of several sensor kinds [19]. For instance, cameras supply detailed visual data, LiDAR provides accurate depth measurements, while IMUs provide motion information.

Bayesian sensor fusion methods are used to model and control uncertainty in measurements made by sensors in probabilistic sensor fusion. Probabilistic models enable the system to make educated decisions even under difficult circumstances by allowing the incorporation of noisy or missing input [18]. The resilience of the perceptual system is improved by this method.

Feature-based Perception: This technique focuses on finding and making use of distinguishing traits in sensor data for mapping and localization. When creating maps and figuring out where the robot is in relation to its surroundings, places of interest, edges, and key points are used as reference points [17]. In surroundings with distinct, recognized elements, feature-based approaches are very helpful.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are used to interpret visual data from cameras in deep learning for perception. CNNs are excellent at tasks like scene interpretation, semantic segmentation, and object recognition [16]. In order to extract the necessary features for precise perception, the machine learns to train CNNs on a variety of datasets.

Figure 4.1.1: Navigation Framework

4.2: Advanced Localization and Mapping Techniques

Robots can explore and navigate complicated surroundings on their own thanks to advanced localization and mapping (SLAM) techniques. These methods enable robots to map their surroundings while also figuring out where they are in relation to that map [15]. To improve the precision, reliability, and effectiveness of SLAM systems, several cutting-edge strategies have surfaced.

The use of loop closure detection in graph SLAM: With nodes denoting robot positions and edges denoting distances between poses, this method depicts the surroundings as a graph [14]. By recognizing already visited sites, loop closure recognition identifies and corrects collected inaccuracies, enhancing the consistency of the output map.

Feature-based and direct methods for visual SLAM: Visual SLAM uses camera data to create maps and determine the pose of the robot. Direct approaches reduce the photometric inaccuracy between successive frames, whereas feature-based methods isolate different features in images [13]. The system is able to create precise and detailed maps in real-time by combining various techniques.

3D SLAM with integration of a LiDAR: The three-dimensional space is expanded by 3D SLAM, which is essential in areas with complex geometries and changing heights [12]. The system can produce accurate 3D point clouds because to the integration of LiDAR data, which allows it to construct precise models of the environment.

Figure 4.2.1: Estimation and Prediction

4.3: Decision-Making and Control Algorithms

Effective decision-making and control algorithms are essential for autonomous robots to intelligently move and engage with their surroundings. Based on how the robot perceives its environment and the objectives it has set, these algorithms decide what actions to perform.

MDPs (Markov Decision Processes): MDPs are a fundamental paradigm for simulating uncertain decision-making. They depict the framework as a collection of states, deeds, probabilities of transition, and rewards [11]. The robot can choose the best course of action for choosing behaviors that maximize anticipated benefits by resolving the MDP.

Reinforcement Learning (RL): RL is a potent model for teaching autonomous entities how to learn from their mistakes and make decisions on their own. Deep Q-Networks (DQN) and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) are examples of algorithms that learn policies through interaction with the environment and reward-based feedback [10]. As a result, the robot can pick up sophisticated decision-making techniques.

Behavior-Based Control: In behavior-based designs, the control system is divided into a number of distinct behaviors, each of which is in charge of a certain function in navigation or interaction [9]. The robot's general conduct develops from the sum of various separate behaviors, which operate simultaneously. This method offers robustness and adaptability in changing circumstances.

Hierarchical Planning: Frameworks for hierarchical planning allow for several levels of abstraction in decision-making. High-level objectives are divided into smaller, more manageable activities that are then planned and carried out by lower-level controllers [8]. As a result, the robot can balance among high-level goals and low-level control, offering an organized method for completing challenging tasks.

4.4: Integration of AI Algorithms with Robotic Platforms

An essential first step in enabling self-driving vehicles to carry out activities intelligibly and adapt to changing contexts is the seamless melding of artificial intelligence with robotic platforms [7]. In order to provide optimal interaction and connection between the AI-driven systems and the real robot, this integration needs both hardware alterations and software implementations.

Hardware modifications are made to the selected robotic platform in order to support the AI algorithms. High-performance computer units, specialized sensors (such as GPUs for quicker processing and LiDAR for environment awareness), and data-exchange communication interfaces may be included as a result.

Development of specific applications to facilitate interaction among AI algorithms and the control systems of the robot is a component of the integration process [6]. Perception, decision-making processes, and control modules can be integrated seamlessly thanks to middleware like Robot Operating System (ROS), which provides a strong framework for controlling the flow of data between various components.

Real-time data processing is necessary for the integrated system to analyze sensor data and take immediate action. To manage the high-speed streams of data produced by sensors, this calls for optimal algorithms and effective software design [5]. To guarantee prompt replies, multithreading strategies and simultaneous processing are frequently used.

Robot control system calibration and synchronization: The robot's control system is tuned to cooperate with the AI algorithms. In order to provide seamless coordination between perception, choices, and action execution, motion control, actuator responses, and feedback chains must be configured.

Protocols for testing and validation Procedures for rigorous testing are devised to confirm the integration's efficacy. This include thorough bench testing to check the functionality of the hardware and software as well as simulation to validate system operation under regulated settings [4]. In order to evaluate performance, hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing mixes digital simulations with actual hardware components.

Figure 4.4.1: Artificial Intelligence

CHAPTER 5: EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION

5.1: Conclusion

The integration of AI and robotics for independent exploration and navigation advances as a result of this study. The system provides a thorough grasp of dynamic surroundings through integration of sensors, perception algorithms, and cutting-edge SLAM techniques. Intelligent navigation is enabled by the use of decision-making algorithms, and real-time response is guaranteed by the effortless integration of AI with the robotic platform. Thorough testing and validation confirm the system's dependability and robustness [3]. This work establishes a basis for self-driving vehicles to effectively traverse and explore complicated surroundings, with broad repercussions for domains including space missions to disaster response. By bridging the gap among theory and application.

5.2 Research Recommendation

It is advised to continue investigating how semantic information might be integrated into perception for better understanding of the world in light of the findings. Investigating novel path planning and obstacle avoidance algorithms in challenging terrains might also improve system flexibility. Additionally, including multi-agent cooperation communication protocols in exploration scenarios may increase the capacities of autonomous systems [2]. Last but not least, integrating AI-robotics platforms will perform at their best thanks to ongoing hardware developments like light and power-efficient sensors. These suggestions will help the development and practical use of autonomous investigation and navigational systems in many challenging and dynamic contexts.

5.3 Future Work

Future work should focus on improving the fusion of AI and robotics by investigating cutting-edge machine learning methods for more flexible decision-making, such as reinforcement learning and deep learning. Researching bio-inspired algorithms may also offer important tips for reliable navigation in challenging circumstances. Perception abilities will also be improved by researching the integration of cutting-edge technologies for sensors like 360-degree LiDAR and sophisticated camera systems [1]. Exciting avenues for future research include investigating the use of AI-robotics convergence in specific fields like underground or extraterrestrial exploration. Additionally, a crucial topic for additional research is the incorporation of ethical issues and safety procedures relevant to self-driving vehicles in harsh environments.

Reference

- 1) Abdel-Latif, K., Epps, R.W., Bateni, F., Han, S., Reyes, K.G. and Abolhasani, M., 2021. Self-driven multistep quantum dot synthesis enabled by autonomous robotic experimentation in flow. *Advanced Intelligent Systems*, 3(2), p.2000245.
- 2) Aboualola, M., Abualsaud, K., Khattab, T., Zorba, N. and Hassanein, H.S., 2023. Edge Technologies for Disaster Management: A Survey of Social Media and Artificial Intelligence Integration. *IEEE Access*.
- 3) Cao, C., Zhu, H., Yang, F., Xia, Y., Choset, H., Oh, J. and Zhang, J., 2022, May. Autonomous exploration development environment and the planning algorithms. In *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (pp. 8921-8928). IEEE.
- 4) Çatal, O., Verbelen, T., Van de Maele, T., Dhoedt, B. and Safron, A., 2021. Robot navigation as hierarchical active inference. *Neural Networks*, 142, pp.192-204.
- 5) Christensen, L., de Gea Fernández, J., Hildebrandt, M., Koch, C.E.S. and Wehbe, B., 2022. Recent advances in ai for navigation and control of underwater robots. *Current Robotics Reports*, 3(4), pp.165-175.
- 6) Cimurs, R., Suh, I.H. and Lee, J.H., 2021. Goal-driven autonomous exploration through deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 7(2), pp.730-737.
- 7) Crespo, J., Castillo, J.C., Mozos, O.M. and Barber, R., 2020. Semantic information for robot navigation: A survey. *Applied Sciences*, 10(2), p.497.

- 8) Dai, A., Papatheodorou, S., Funk, N., Tzoumanikas, D. and Leutenegger, S., 2020, May. Fast frontier-based information-driven autonomous exploration with a mav. In *2020 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA)* (pp. 9570-9576). IEEE.
- 9) Gan, C., GU, Y., Zhou, S., Schwartz, J., Alter, S., Traer, J., Gutfreund, D., Tenenbaum, J.B., McDermott, J.H. and Torralba, A., 2022. Finding fallen objects via asynchronous audio-visual integration. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 10523-10533).
- 10) Gan, C., Zhou, S., Schwartz, J., Alter, S., Bhandwaldar, A., Gutfreund, D., Yamins, D.L., DiCarlo, J.J., McDermott, J., Torralba, A. and Tenenbaum, J.B., 2022, May. The threedworld transport challenge: A visually guided task-and-motion planning benchmark towards physically realistic embodied ai. In *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (pp. 8847-8854). IEEE.
- 11) Grigore, L.S., Priescu, I., Joita, D. and Oncioiu, I., 2020. The integration of collaborative robot systems and their environmental impacts. *Processes*, 8(4), p.494.
- 12) Hoorfar, H., Kosarirad, H., Taheri, N., Fathi, F. and Bagheri, A., 2023. Concealing Robots in Environments: Enhancing Navigation and Privacy through Stealth Integration. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on AI and Robotics*, 2.
- 13) Hu, J., Niu, H., Carrasco, J., Lennox, B. and Arvin, F., 2020. Voronoi-based multi-robot autonomous exploration in unknown environments via deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 69(12), pp.14413-14423.
- 14) Islam, N., Haseeb, K., Almogren, A., Din, I.U., Guizani, M. and Altameem, A., 2020. A framework for topological based map building: A solution to autonomous robot navigation in smart cities. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 111, pp.644-653.
- 15) Josphineleela, R., Periasamy, S., Krishnaveni, N., Prasad, D.S., Rao, B.V., Garde, M.J. and Gore, S., 2023. Exploration beyond Boundaries: AI-Based Advancements in Rover Robotics for Lunar Missions Space like Chandrayaan. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 11(10s), pp.640-648.
- 16) Kästner, L., Marx, C. and Lambrecht, J., 2020, August. Deep-reinforcement-learning-based semantic navigation of mobile robots in dynamic environments. In *2020 IEEE 16th International Conference on Automation Science and Engineering (CASE)* (pp. 1110-1115). IEEE.
- 17) Kolar, P., Benavidez, P. and Jamshidi, M., 2020. Survey of datafusion techniques for laser and vision based sensor integration for autonomous navigation. *Sensors*, 20(8), p.2180.
- 18) Krell, E., Sheta, A., Balasubramanian, A.P.R. and King, S.A., 2019. Collision-free autonomous robot navigation in unknown environments utilizing PSO for path planning. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing Research*, 9.
- 19) Lindqvist, B., Kanellakis, C., Mansouri, S.S., Agha-mohammadi, A.A. and Nikolakopoulos, G., 2022. Compra: A compact reactive autonomy framework for subterranean mav based search-and-rescue operations. *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, 105(3), p.49.
- 20) Mac, T.T., Lin, C.Y., Huan, N.G., Duc, L., Nhat, P.C.H. and Hai, H.H., 2021. Hybrid SLAM-based exploration of a mobile robot for 3D scenario reconstruction and autonomous navigation. *Acta Polytech. Hung*, 18, pp.197-212.
- 21) Möller, R., Furnari, A., Battiato, S., Härmä, A. and Farinella, G.M., 2021. A survey on human-aware robot navigation. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 145, p.103837.
- 22) Ohradzansky, M.T., Mills, A.B., Rush, E.R., Riley, D.G., Frew, E.W. and Humbert, J.S., 2020, May. Reactive control and metric-topological planning for exploration. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (pp. 4073-4079). IEEE.

- 23) Rajendran, G., Uma, V. and O'Brien, B., 2022. Unified robot task and motion planning with extended planner using ROS simulator. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, 34(9), pp.7468-7481.
- 24) Rayhan, A., 2023. Artificial intelligence in robotics: From automation to autonomous systems.
- 25) Reinhart, R., Dang, T., Hand, E., Papachristos, C. and Alexis, K., 2020, May. Learning-based path planning for autonomous exploration of subterranean environments. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (pp. 1215-1221). IEEE.
- 26) Rezwan, S. and Choi, W., 2022. Artificial intelligence approaches for UAV navigation: Recent advances and future challenges. *IEEE Access*, 10, pp.26320-26339.
- 27) Rezwan, S. and Choi, W., 2022. Artificial intelligence approaches for UAV navigation: Recent advances and future challenges. *IEEE Access*, 10, pp.26320-26339.
- 28) Staroverov, A., Yudin, D.A., Belkin, I., Adeshkin, V., Solomentsev, Y.K. and Panov, A.I., 2020. Real-time object navigation with deep neural networks and hierarchical reinforcement learning. *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.195608-195621.
- 29) Tullu, A., Endale, B., Wondosen, A. and Hwang, H.Y., 2021. Machine learning approach to real-time 3D path planning for autonomous navigation of unmanned aerial vehicle. *Applied Sciences*, 11(10), p.4706.
- 30) Xia, P., Xu, F., Zhu, Q. and Du, J., 2022. Human robot comparison in rapid structural inspection. In *Construction Research Congress 2022* (pp. 570-580).
- 31) Xie, D., Chen, L., Liu, L., Chen, L. and Wang, H., 2022. Actuators and sensors for application in agricultural robots: A review. *Machines*, 10(10), p.913.
- 32) Xie, L., Miao, Y., Wang, S., Blunsom, P., Wang, Z., Chen, C., Markham, A. and Trigoni, N., 2020. Learning with stochastic guidance for robot navigation. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 32(1), pp.166-176.
- 33) Yip, M., Salcudean, S., Goldberg, K., Althoefer, K., Menciassi, A., Opfermann, J.D., Krieger, A., Swaminathan, K., Walsh, C.J., Huang, H. and Lee, I.C., 2023. Artificial intelligence meets medical robotics. *Science*, 381(6654), pp.141-146.
- 34) Zeng, F., Wang, C. and Ge, S.S., 2020. A survey on visual navigation for artificial agents with deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.135426-135442.
- 35) Zhang, J., Yang, X., Wang, W., Guan, J., Ding, L. and Lee, V.C., 2023. Automated guided vehicles and autonomous mobile robots for recognition and tracking in civil engineering. *Automation in Construction*, 146, p.104699.